

1 **B3GALT6 is activated in response to ERBB2 growth factor inhibition and associated with**
2 **resistance to trastuzumab.**

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7 Growth factor signaling pathways are prototypical signaling pathways whose basic characteristics in a
8 cancer cell include a stereotyped feedback response behavior. EGFR family signaling pathways include
9 ERBB1-4, like ERBB2 (HER2). Trastuzumab (Herceptin) is used for the treatment of HER2+ breast cancer
10 in humans. Here we describe *B3GALT6* as a gene product induced following growth factor inhibition in
11 human cells and following HER2+ inhibition resulting from treatment with trastuzumab in humans.
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